

CHARACTERISTICS AND TECHNOLOGY OF OBTAINING DRY EXTRACT OF COMMON RASPBERRY (*RUBUS IDAEUS*), GROWING IN SOUTHERN KAZAKHSTAN

Turebekova G. A.¹

Daurenbekov K. N.²

JSC South Kazakhstan Medical Academy, Shymkent, Republic of Kazakhstan

e-mail: gulya_t.a@mail.ru

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17321560>

Relevance: Common raspberry (*Rubus idaeus*) is the most common berry bush, possessing high nutritional and biologically active properties. Southern Kazakhstan, with its diverse climate and rich flora, offers unique opportunities for studying and using raspberries.

Objective: to develop a technology for obtaining a dry extract from common raspberry leaves, preserving the high content of biologically active substances and obtaining a high-quality product for use in pharmaceuticals.

Research methods: 1. Collection and preparation of raw materials: Red raspberry leaves were collected during the growing season, when they contain the maximum amount of biologically active substances. The optimal collection period is June-July.

2. Drying the leaves: To preserve the maximum amount of biologically active substances, gentle drying was used at a temperature no higher than 40-50°C. Drying duration : 6-8 hours, until the raw material moisture content reached less than 10%.

3. Grinding: The dried leaves were ground to a powder with a particle size of 0.5-1 mm.

4. Extraction: A 70% ethanol solution was used, as it is considered the most suitable solvent for extracting flavonoids, tannins, and organic acids. The raw material to solvent ratio was 1:10 (one part dry raw material to 10 parts solvent). Extraction method: The raw material was infused at room temperature for 24-48 hours with periodic stirring. Extraction was carried out under reflux at 40-60°C for 2-4 hours. This method accelerates the process and increases the yield of active substances.

5. Extract purification: The resulting solution was filtered to remove solid particles. Paper and membrane filters were used. The purified extract was evaporated on a rotary evaporator at a temperature no higher than 40°C until the volume was reduced by 5-10 times.

6. Obtaining a dry extract: the dry extract is a light to dark green powder with a characteristic odor and taste. Moisture content is no more than 5%.

7. The content of biologically active substances was determined using spectrophotometric and chromatographic methods.

Research results: using this technology, we obtained a high-quality dry extract of common raspberry, which will retain its medicinal properties (Table 1):

Table 1. Results of quantitative analysis

Flavonoids	0.4%
Tannins	from 2-5%
Vitamin C (ascorbic acid)	0.03% -0.1%
Vitamin E (tocopherol)	0.001-0.002%
B vitamins (including B1, B2, B3, B6).	0.001-0.01%

Conclusions: The developed technology for producing a dry extract from common raspberry leaves preserves the high content of biologically active substances, such as flavonoids, tannins, and

MPHAPP

THE 6TH INTERNATIONAL SCIENTIFIC AND PRACTICAL
CONFERENCE "MODERN PHARMACEUTICS: ACTUAL
PROBLEMS AND PROSPECTS"
TASHKENT, OCTOBER 17, 2025

in-academy.uz

organic acids. The dry extract can be used as an ingredient in pharmaceuticals and dietary supplements.